

Addition compounds of As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III} halides with quinoline and iso-quinoline

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Abstract : A few addition compounds of As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III} halides containing quinoline and iso-quinoline have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, UV, NMR and molar conductance studies. The complexes have the compositions [MX₃.L], where M = As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III}, L = quinoline and iso-quinoline, X = Br⁻, Cl⁻.

Keywords : Addition compounds, quinoline, iso-quinoline.

The present paper reports the preparation and characterization of six new addition compounds of As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III} halides with quinoline and iso-quinoline.

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The molar conductance values reveal that these are non-electrolytic in nature¹. The values of molar susceptibility indicate that the compounds are diamagnetic². From the analytical and physical data the general formula of the complexes can be given as [MX₃.L], where M = As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III}; X = Br⁻, Cl⁻; L =

quinoline and iso-quinoline.

The IR spectra (Table 3) of the compounds have shown medium bands in the region 3100–3000 cm⁻¹, are assigned to the (C–H) stretching frequencies and the bands observed around 1270–1235 cm⁻¹ indicated (C=N) and (C=C) modes respectively. Both the bands are shifted considerable to lower frequencies after the adduct formation. The most significant bands in all the compounds in the region 320–295 cm⁻¹ are undoubtedly assigned for the (M–N) modes³ which indicated that the adduct formation has taken place through nitrogen atom of quinoline ring. All the compounds under investigation are found

Table 1. Analytical data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compd. (color)	Molecular weight	Decom. point (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Molar susceptibility (χ _g × 10 ⁻³)
				M	C	H	N		
1.	AsBr ₃ .qiq (White)	430 (443.78)	185	15.00 (16.88)	25.00 (24.35)	1.25 (1.58)	3.50 (3.16)	23.75	-0.780
2.	SbCl ₃ .qiq (White)	340 (357.31)	193	34.00 (34.07)	28.50 (30.24)	1.50 (1.96)	3.25 (3.92)	26.78	-0.700
3.	BiCl ₃ .qiq (White)	425 (444.45)	220	46.50 (47.01)	23.00 (24.31)	1.50 (1.58)	3.00 (3.15)	22.84	-0.850
4.	AsBr ₃ .qiq' (White)	440 (443.78)	196	15.50 (16.88)	25.25 (24.35)	1.45 (1.58)	3.20 (3.16)	24.22	-0.920
5.	SbCl ₃ .qiq' (White)	350 (357.31)	205	33.50 (34.07)	29.56 (30.24)	1.50 (1.96)	3.60 (3.92)	27.78	-0.750
6.	BiCl ₃ .qiq' (White)	435 (444.51)	222	46.00 (47.01)	23.85 (24.31)	1.60 (1.58)	3.50 (3.15)	21.92	-0.880

qiq = quinoline, qiq' = iso-quinoline.

Note

Table 2. The heat of neutralization calculated as the amount of heat evolved per mole of the acid (base solution taken in excess in reaction) at 30 °C

Sl. no.	Compd.	Molar ratio (acid : base)	Strength of MX ₃ in EtOH (S)	Volume of MX ₃ in EtOH (V cm ³)	Weight of the solution (w ₁ g)	Weight of (cal + stir) (w ₂ g)	Specific heat of solution (S ₁)	Specific heat of (cal + stir) (S ₂)	Heat involve from graph (t ₂ - t ₁)	-ΔH (kcal/mol)	Average -ΔH
1.	AsBr ₃ .qiq	1 : 0.410	0.502	30	24.68	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.78	12.45	
2.	SbCl ₃ .qiq	1 : 0.567	0.504	30	24.22	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.75	12.21	12.54
3.	BiCl ₃ .qiq	1 : 0.409	0.501	30	24.05	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.88	12.97	
4.	AsBr ₃ .qiq'	1 : 0.411	0.501	30	24.12	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.85	12.98	12.98
5.	SbCl ₃ .qiq'	1 : 0.566	0.503	30	24.48	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.86	12.76	
6.	BiCl ₃ .qiq'	1 : 0.402	0.502	30	24.77	88.01	0.579	0.669	2.95	13.22	

to be diamagnetic and their electronic spectra exhibit bands in region 227–361 nm, which are assigned as charged transfer band⁴.

The chemical shift (δ) values of the α -protons in the quinoline ring are found to move down field after adduct formation, which may be accounted for nearly developed positive charge on the quinoline-nitrogen. A multiplet around $\delta = 7.6$ ppm is observed due to fused benzene ring is pyridine nucleus in all the compound and a doublet is shown at 7.59 ppm for (-N-CH₂-CH=CH₂-) and (-N-CH=CH₂-) respectively. A doublet at $\delta 7.16$ ppm in compound (1) and $\delta 8.97$ ppm in compounds (2, 3) due to (-N=CH-CH₂-).

The enthalpies (heat of neutralization including heat of precipitation) ΔH reported here are believed to be new and significant. The values of heat of neutralization of MX₃ [M = As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III}; X = Cl⁻, Br⁻] with N-donor ligands viz. qiq and qiq' in ethanol are recorded in the Table 2. Arsenic(III) bromide, antimony(III) chloride and bismuth(III) chloride have been found to form 1 : 1 solid adducts with electron donor qiq and qiq' and associated with the evolution of average 12.54 and 12.98 kcal/mol of the base respectively.

As the solvent does not take part in the chemical reaction, acids and bases are therefore, free to exhibit their intrinsic strengths. Heat of reaction is thus mainly due to the adducts formation and its precipitation from the solvents. It is generally agreed that the heat of neutralization

(enthalpy change, $-\Delta H$) is a fairly reliable measure of the strength of acids and bases⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and used as supplied by E. Merck and B.D.H. Ltd. Ethanol was purified by refluxing the crude 99% product with iodine and magnesium turnings. A solution of L (0.01 m) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) was added dropwise, with stirring, to an ethanolic solution (50 ml) of metal(III) halide (0.01 m) in warm condition. The resulting mixture was then refluxed for seven hours and cooled. Then the volume of this solution was reduced to 50 ml by heating on a hot plate and cooled in a freezer for two days. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator charged with fused calcium chloride.

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on JNM-PMX 60 NMR spectrometer. The solvents were deaerated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-*d*₆). Resonance were quoted of the δ scale relative to tetramethyl silane (TMS, $\delta=0$) as an internal standard. The IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer as KBr pellets in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹ and in the range 200–900 nm as nujol mulls CsI windows. Conductivities of 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ solutions of the complexes in DMSO were measured at 28 °C using a WPACM 35 conductivity meter and dip-type cell with platinized electrodes. The decomposition points of the complexes were recorded with an electrothermal melting point apparatus. The molecular weight of the complexes were determined in nitrogen by the cryoscopic method. As^{III}, Sb^{III} and Bi^{III} were determined complexometrically⁶ with a standard solution of EDTA using mureoxide indicator.

Table 3. IR bands for the ligands and the complexes

	$\nu(\text{C-H})$	$\nu(\text{C=N}), \nu(\text{C=C})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$
Ligands	3250	2200–1600	730 (H ₂ O medium)
Complexes	3100–3000	1270–1235	320–295

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